

Supplementary Figure S1. A best scoring Maximum Likelihood tree that includes only strains with complete sequence data available for four loci (*gapdh*, *tubb*, ITS rDNA and *tef1- α*). The tree shows the relationships of *Trichophyton spiralisforme* sp. nov. and *Trichophyton persicum* sp. nov. to other dermatophytes belonging to the *T. benhamiae* complex. Ex-type isolates are designated by a superscript T. *Trichophyton rubrum* CBS 202.88 was used as the outgroup.